

Research Article

Artificial intelligence and institutional members' academic integrity issues: The role of educational administrators

D. B. Gayus^a, O. G. Agbor^a & A. Mohammed^{a*}

^a Department of Educational Foundations, Federal College of Education, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Abstract

Technology has gain prominence in all sectors and education is not excluded. Use of AI tools is the order of the day in academic activities. Both teachers and students have come to find AI tools as significant aspects that can be used conveniently in the teaching and learning process; including research and other related fields. This necessitates the need for educational administrators to device check and balances in the usage of AI while guarding institutional and academic integrity. The paper therefore highlights the impact of AI and academic integrity, the role of educational administrators in AI and academic integrity and various strategies used in maintaining academic integrity in AI usage. These strategies which include: awareness on Academic integrity, well defined policies on AI usage, promoting integrity culture, proper monitoring and supervision of institutional members, plagiarism detection tools and clear penalty for offenders were discussed. Recommendations were made that: institutional members should be sensitized on the positive use of AI tools and the consequences of academic dishonesty, well defined policies should be developed on AI usage and academic integrity and the penalty for offenders should be clearly defined, integrity culture should be promoted among institutional members, proper monitoring and supervision should be well established in checking any inappropriate behavior and that plagiarism detection tools should be used to guard against academic dishonesty while maintaining academic integrity.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Institutional Members, Academic Integrity, Educational Administrators

1. Introduction

Education is the basis for world development. No nation or society can develop to its maximum capacity without educating its citizens. Kumar (n.d) made reference to Ghandhi's statement that "education means an all- round drawing out of the best in child and man-body, mind and spirit". By implication, this signifies that Education is the all-round development of citizens socially, morally, intellectually, politically and in all other aspects of life. Hence nations and states use education to achieve what they intend to achieve in their development.

Many changes have occurred in education today and such changes cannot be divorced from the changing trends in the society associated mainly with the scientific and technological developments. Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration in to the education system has open ways for ease in study, teaching and research. However, it has also as well exposed some students and lecturers who are the institutional members to dishonest acts in carrying out their academic

responsibilities. Academic Integrity deals with both students and teachers honesty, respect and trustworthiness in handling learning and teaching responsibilities. It entails in this context, dealing with educational resources and materials with honesty and trustworthiness.

Students often use AI for writing their assignments, projects and other academic activities, similarly, lecturers use AI to generate their lecture notes and to conduct research, this made it necessary for measures to be put in place for checking both students and lecturer's academic integrity for using such tools. This paper therefore dwells on the role of educational administrators in enhancing a positive way of using AI while maintaining both students and staff academic integrity which is directly linked to institutional academic integrity.

An Educational Administrator is a person or leader saddled with the responsibility of managing both human and material resources through obtaining the cooperation,

*Corresponding author: A. Mohammed

Email: aminamohammed@fcecyla.edu.ng (A. Mohammed)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2832-0272>

Received: 20/10/2025; Accepted: 23/11/2025; Published: 30/11/2025

participation, intervention and involvement of many people (staff, students, parents; community) in order to accomplish the goals and objectives of the institution.

Educational administrators use of strategies such as creating awareness on proper use of AI, well defined institutional policies on AI usage, proper monitoring and supervision strategies, use of plagiarism detection tools, promotion of integrity culture, penalties and sanctions for offender can enhance positive use of AI and maintaining academic integrity.

2. Concepts of Artificial Intelligence and Academic Integrity

Artificial Intelligence (AI) according to National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA, 2024) refers “to computer systems that can perform complex tasks normally done by human-reasoning, decision making and creating; and also an artificial system developed in computer software, physical hardware or other context that solves tasks requiring human-like perception, cognition, planning, learning, communication or physical action”. By implication, AI in education can therefore be viewed as the use of computer systems that performs the tasks typically associated with human reasoning that can enhance research, teaching and learning.

Marais (2022) defines academic integrity as a “commitment to the key values of honesty, trust, fairness, equity, respect and responsibility and the translation of these values in to action”. In the same vein, International Centre for Academic Integrity (ICAI) cited in Sozon, Alkharabsheh, Fong and Chuan (2024) defines Academic integrity “as a commitment not only to uphold ethical values, but also to demonstrate behaviors that promote six fundamental principles “honesty, trust, fairness, respect, responsibility and courage” in all aspects of education, research and scholarly communication within the context of higher education”. The European Network for Academic Integrity (ENAI) in Balalle and Pannilage (2025) defines Academic Integrity as “compliance with ethical and professional principles, standards, practices and consistent system of values that serve as guidance for making decisions and taking actions in education, research and scholarship”.

McCabe et al cited in Celik and Razi (2023) propose six reasons why there should be care for academic integrity: Integrity is the cornerstone of academia, Cheating is widespread and on the rise, College years are critical period for ethical development, College students face significant pressures to cheat, Students are being taught that cheating is acceptable, and Today’s college students represent tomorrow’s leaders.

From these reasons we can deduce that no academic institution can succeed when its institutional members engage in cheating and other forms of academic fraud, when its institutional members are not ethically upright in the academic pursuit, when institutional members are given a

reason to engage in academic dishonesty or when such is considered as acceptable to institutional members. Institutional members especially the students are the leaders of tomorrow while the teachers are those responsible to mold their behavior and equally serve as role models for them to emulate. On this basis, educational administrators should guard the institutional members against improper usage of AI tools for enhancement of academic integrity. This can be done through proper supervision and monitoring of institutional members on plagiarism issues especially in research.

3. Impact of AI usage in teaching and Learning

According to Vieriu and Pettrea (2025), majority of the respondents (students) believe that AI enhances their academic performance in exams, projects and grades thereby improving their results. The students equally believe that it improves their learning by giving them quick access to educational resources, reduce time needed to get information and enhance organization of academic activities

AI can enhance interactive learning environments, provide instant feedback and equally keep students actively involved in the teaching/learning processes. It can carry students with learning disabilities along thereby enhancing inclusive education (Ofem and Chukwujama, 2024). In essence AI creates an avenue for all learners and teachers to have access to learning resources irrespective of their condition or the environment where they find themselves; provided that they have internet access.

At the institutional level, AI can enable teachers and educational administrators to allocate resources efficiently and take better decisions on programmes, students support services and appropriate planning mechanisms (Ofem and Chukwujama, 2024). AI can guide the teachers and educational administrators on the appropriate mechanisms needed to be put in place for a better resource allocation, effective decision making on programmes, provision for students support services and good planning mechanisms for the development of the institution.

Academic integrity supports learning opportunities and guard against plagiarism, contract cheatings and test banks that deprive students of learning opportunities. Academic integrity leads to accurate students learning and serves as an indicator of workplace behavior (Lee, 2022). The use of AI in teaching and learning processes should be done with caution taking in to cognizance ethical considerations in guarding against theft of knowledge and educational resources.

4. Educational Administrators and Academic Integrity

Educational Administrators have a significant role to play in ensuring that academic wrong doings are not condoned in their institutions. This can be enhanced through putting necessary measures on ground for effective monitoring and supervision of both staff and students.

Teacher should be properly guided to guard against any act that leads to the misuse of AI while discharging their responsibilities. Students equally need to be directed on the ethics necessary for effective use of AI especially in writing their assignments, projects or thesis.

In a study conducted by Hamad and Charles (2024), it was found out that school leaders control online assessments, update assessment policy to meet the changing need in education and equally come up with measures to enhance academic integrity especially through plagiarism identification techniques. This signifies that educational administrators are saddled with the responsibility of putting measures on ground to ensure that the ethics of using AI in teaching and learning processes are well guarded for academic integrity of the institution to be maintained.

Academic integrity of any institution is one of the cardinal responsibilities of an educational administrator. An institution known with academic fraud such as plagiarism, contract cheating, direct copying or theft of academic resources either from its students or teachers will end up losing its prestige. Certificates coming from such institution may not be recognized and the graduates may be at the receiving end of such consequences. Similarly, teachers coming from such institutions may lose their respect in the midst of other academicians; thereby leading to further disregard for the institution.

Educational Administrators are responsible for examining their institutional practices in an effort to develop norms and practices aimed to checkmate factors that may contribute to academic misconduct (Prescott, 1989). The use of AI if not properly guarded by educational administrator through proper measures and constant checking may lead to the downfall of an entire institution.

5. Strategies for maintaining Academic Integrity in the usage of AI

Technology has made it easier to copy and paste materials that are readily available on the internet, thereby facilitating academic misconduct, it equally makes it easier to contract academic work to others; leading to contract cheating, of recent is the issue of the use of AI bots such as ChatGPT and OpenAI to specify academic work needed to be done (Johnson, 2023). Availability and exposure to the use of these technological developments necessitates the need for educational administrators to checkmate the use of these avenues in the teaching, learning and research in their institutions. The following are some of the measures educational administrators can use to maintain academic integrity of their institution especially in the use of AI tools.

Awareness on Academic Integrity: Instilling proper awareness of what academic integrity entails can enhance ethical behavior in both staff and students. Institutions can equally safeguard reputations and ensure positive contributions in academic activities. These ethical behaviors can raise the institutions awareness of academic dishonesty and its consequences thereby creating an enabling

environment that frowns against cheating and other academic frauds (Lee, 2023). Both staff and students should be properly educated on what constitute appropriate and inappropriate behaviors in the use of AI tools and the likely consequences of engaging in inappropriate behavior.

Well Defined Policies: comprehensive academic integrity policies on AI usage should be developed by institutions. Proper guidelines should be well spell out for institutional members to know and abide by appropriately. Educational administrators can equally have a well written policy guideline for their institutions which clearly defines the ethics needed to be followed by their staff and students in the usage of AI and guarding their academic integrity. Equally the policy should clearly define the measures needed to be put in place by the institution on this direction.

Proper Monitoring and Supervision: universities and other higher education institutions have put in efforts in the monitoring and controlling the use of AI through the use of various measures to curtail academic dishonesty. Such measures include; creating awareness amongst staff and students on academic integrity and the consequences of academic dishonesty. Proper monitoring and supervision if carried out should curtail cases of plagiarism and contract cheating on the part of staff and students thereby enhancing academic integrity.

Plagiarism Detection Tools: academic dishonesty is becoming an alarming issue in higher education today; where instances prevail on lecturers copying others PhD thesis and claiming it as their own. Perkins, Gezgin and Roe (2020) are of the view that plagiarism entails acts such as contract cheating through which individuals or organizations are contracted to carry out academic work on others behalf. Plagiarism according to Sozon, Alkharabsheh, Fong and Chuan (2024) is “using another individuals thoughts, words, phrases, sentences, or facts and taking them as one’s own” Hence, Balalle and Pannilage (2025) are of the view that plagiarism is the primary component of academic integrity and various terms such as contract cheating, ghostwriting and AI writing are directly linked to academic integrity.

To handle plagiarism issues, educational administrators can make use of AI detection software (such as turnitin) that can detect AI generated contents (Lee, 2023). whether the plagiarism is carried out by student, staff or through contract cheating, tools such as Turnitin (<https://www.turnitin.com>), Plagscan (<https://www.plagscan.com>) and Urkund (<https://www.orkund.com>) are excellent in carrying out text-matching issues and plagiarism checking (Johnson, 2023).

Promoting Integrity Culture: to create a positive academic integrity culture, deliberate effort should be geared towards change in the belief, values and attitude of students and faculty through a visionary and courageous leadership, creation of academic integrity policies and involvement of experts (Celik and Razi, 2023). Educational administrators need to go an extra mile in creating a positive culture that disabuses the mind of both staff and students from academic

dishonesty and fraud. There is the need to work for an enabling environment where morale is boosted towards respect for one's self and others academic work which in turn may disabuse the mind of institutional members from academic dishonesty while enhancing integrity culture in AI usage. Encouragement for engaging in critical thinking rather than copying someone's work and emphasis on contents with originality is prerequisite to the development of integrity culture.

Clear Penalty for Offenders: effective strategies should be clearly developed for dealing with academic misconduct. Appropriate sanctions should be clearly defined for every offence committed. For instance, in a study conducted by Celik and Razi (2023) it was revealed that Ministry of National Education Turkiye prescribed four sanctions against academic integrity violations: reprimand, temporary suspensions, school change and expulsion from formal education, however, cases of academic misconducts such as plagiarism, fabrication and contract cheating were not included in the regulation as violations. Educational Administrators can equally create clear penalties for all academic dishonesty in the usage of AI engaged by the institutional members. Such penalties should be meted on any institutional member found wanting; hence a strong guard against AI abuse in academic activities.

5. Conclusion

The paper dwells on the role of educational administrators on maintaining academic integrity in the usage of AI. The concepts of AI and academic integrity and the impact of academic integrity were discussed. The roles of educational administrators in enhancing positive usage of AI by institutional members were highlighted. The paper discussed strategies necessary for maintaining academic integrity in the usage of AI to include; awareness on Academic integrity, well defined policies on AI usage, promoting integrity culture, proper monitoring and supervision, plagiarism detection tools and clear penalty for offenders.

Recommendations:

The following are recommended for the enhancement of academic integrity by educational administrators:

- Institutional members should be sensitized on the positive use of AI tools and the consequences of academic dishonesty for teaching and learning activities.
- Well defined policies should be developed on AI usage and academic integrity and any offender should be penalized for the act committed.
- Integrity culture should be promoted among institutional members so as to guard against academic dishonesty.
- Monitoring and supervision should be well established in checking any behavior detrimental to AI usage and academic integrity.
- Plagiarism detection tools should be used to guard against

academic dishonesty while maintaining academic integrity.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
ICAI	International Centre for Academic Integrity
ENAI	European Network for Academic Integrity

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the contribution of Federal College of education, Yola whose internet facilities were used for this research and all authors whose works are cited in the paper.

Author Contributions

Gayus, Diana B.: Conceptualization, Writing- original draft,
Agbor, Ogar Godwin: Writing-Review and Editing
Mohammed, Amina: Conceptualization, writing-Review and Editing.

Conflicts of Interest

The author(s) declare that they have no known competing financial interests, professional affiliations or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper,

Funding

None

References

- Balalle, H., & Pannilage, S. (2025). Reassessing academic integrity in the age of AI: a systemic literature review on AI and academic integrity. *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, 11, Article 101299. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101299>
- Celik, O., & Razi, S. (2023). Facilitators and barriers to creating a culture of academic integrity at secondary schools: An exploratory case study. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 19 (4), 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-023-00125-4>
- Hamad, H. A., & Charles, T. (2024). The role of educational leaders in ensuring academic integrity with online assessments. *Open Journal of Leadership*, 13 (2), 154-167. DOI: 10.4236/ojl.2024.132010
- Johnson, C. (2023). Understanding academic integrity and plagiarism in the digital age: Can digital forensics techniques help prevent and detect academic misconduct? A submission presented in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the University of South Wales/Prifysgol

- De Cymru for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy
- Kumar, R. (n.d). Gandhi on value of education in Ghandian View on education. Available online amsevagaram.org
- Lee, C. (2022). Why academic integrity is important to teaching and learning. Retrieved 1/10/2025 @ <https://www.nassp.org/2022/1>
- Lee, C. (2023). AI plagiarism changers: how academic leaders can prepare institutions. Retrieved 01/10/2025. Available @ turnitin.com
- Marais, I. E. (2022). Institutionalization of academic integrity: experiences at a distance education university in South Africa during COVID-19. *CrisTal Critical Studies in Teaching and Learning*, 10 (2), 57-79. Doi:10.14426/cristal.v10i2.585
- National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) (2024). What is Artificial Intelligence. Retrieved 02/10/2025 @ nasa.gov/what-is-artifi...
- Ofem., U.J., & Chukwujama, G. (2024). Sustainable artificial intelligence-driven classroom assessment in higher institutions: lessons from Estonia, China, the USA and Australia for Nigeria. *European Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Education*, 5 (2), 1-12, e02403, <https://doi.org/10.30935/ejimed/15265>
- Perkins, M., Gezgin, U.B., & Roe, J. (2020). Reducing plagiarism through academic misconduct education. *International Journal of Educational Integrity*, 16 (3). Article 00052-8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-020-00052-8>
- Prescott, P. A. (1989). Academic misconduct: considerations for educational administrators. Retrieved 1/10/2025 @ [https://doi.org/10.1016/8755-7223\(89\)90041-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/8755-7223(89)90041-0)
- Sozon, Md., Alkharabsheh, O. H. M., Fong, P. W., & Chuan, S. B. (2024). Cheating and Plagiarism in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs): A Literature Review. Retrieved 1/10/2025 @ <https://www.doi.org/0.5064/F6NEG17I> (Sozon et.al.2024c)
- Vieriu, A. M. and Pettrea, G. (2025). The impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Students Academic Development. *Education Sciences*, 15 (3), 343. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15030343>